

Run-4/5/6 measurement of the muon anomalous magnetic moment by the Muon $g-2$ experiment at FNAL

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Abstract

The Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory (FNAL) Muon $g - 2$ Experiment is designed to measure the muon's anomalous magnetic moment, $a_\mu = (g - 2)/2$ with an accuracy of 140 parts per billion. This quantity is determined from two key measurements; the difference between the muon's spin precession frequency and its cyclotron frequency, given by $\omega_a = \omega_s - \omega_c$, and $\tilde{\omega}'_p$, proportional to the muon-weighted magnetic field. In this talk, we present the final result from the muon $g-2$ collaboration and analysis techniques based on data collected from 2020 to 2023 (Run-4/5/6). The new measurement aligns with both the earlier FNAL results and the Brookhaven experiment. The muon anomaly is measured to be $a_\mu(\text{Run-4/5/6}) = 116\,592\,0710(162) \times 10^{-12}$ (139 ppb) and $a_\mu(\text{Run-1-6}) = 116\,592\,0705(148) \times 10^{-12}$ (127 ppb).

1 The Muon $g-2$

The magnetic moment $\vec{\mu}$ of a fundamental particle with mass m , charge q and spin \vec{S} can be expressed

$$\vec{\mu} = g \frac{q}{2m} \vec{S} \quad (1)$$

where g is the gyromagnetic ratio, a dimensionless quantity which describes the strength of the magnetic moment. Schwinger's 1948 calculation of the electron gyromagnetic ratio demonstrated that g differs from the Dirac theory prediction of 2 [1]. This difference arises from the interaction of a given lepton with virtual particles, which provide an additional contribution to the g -factor and can be parametrised in terms of the magnetic anomaly $a = \frac{g-2}{2}$.

The electron g -factor in the Standard Model has been calculated to an astonishing precision, and the electron anomalous magnetic moment is found to agree with its experimental measurement [3]. However, the muon anomalous magnetic moment has presented physicists with a puzzle that has persisted for over 20 years. The E821 experiment conducted at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) [2] measured the muon magnetic anomaly with a relative precision of 0.54 parts per million (ppm), revealing a discrepancy of nearly 3σ from the SM prediction [8]. By 2017, improvements in the SM calculations increased this discrepancy to 3.7σ , marking it as one of the most pronounced differences between experimental data and SM predictions. To further investigate this discrepancy and improve the precision of the measurement, the E989 muon $g-2$ experiment was launched at Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory (FNAL), and started data collection in 2018. Although the differences between the experimental measurement and the Standard Model (SM) predictions have been gradually shrinking, the possible presence of

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Figure 1: View of the muon g-2 experimental setup at FNAL. The most notable feature is a storage ring covered in a white insulating blanket [8].

particles beyond the SM has not been ruled out due to differences in theoretical predictions. The final published result from the FNAL experiment, using data taken in the years 2020-2023 (Run-4/5/6), [7] will be discussed here. This is the highest precision measurement of muon g-2 and will remain so for many years to come.

2 The Muon g-2 Experiment at FNAL

The Muon g-2 experiment at FNAL was set up with the design aim of measuring the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon to a precision of 0.14 ppm, a fourfold improvement in precision with respect to the BNL experiment [5]. The experiment uses positively charged muons produced by the FNAL accelerator complex. FNAL houses a linear accelerator where protons reach energies up to 400 MeV before being injected into a booster ring where they can reach 8 GeV. A fixed target is used to produce high energy positive pions; 3.1 GeV pions are then selected and separated from protons. The resulting muon beam, a product of pion decay, is 95% spin-polarised, a feature that is crucial to the experimental principle of the muon g-2 experiment.

2.1 Experimental Setup

The main feature of the muon g-2 experimental apparatus is a 3.56 m radius 1.45 T superferric magnetic storage ring which has been recycled from the BNL experiment. The ring is used to confine the polarised muon beam through a series of three superconducting coils that span the circumference of the steel yoke providing a uniform magnetic field throughout. Figure 1 shows an aerial view of this ring with insulation in place. The muons are confined vertically using four electrostatic quadrupoles (ESQ) that are placed symmetrically around the ring.

There are three types of detectors used to make this precision measurement. The first type consists of 24 electromagnetic calorimeters made of lead fluoride (PbF_2) crystals spaced around the interior of the ring [9]; these are used to measure the energy of the positrons decaying from the muons. Each crystal is coupled to a silicon photomultiplier readout. The second type consists of two straw-tube tracker stations used to measure the stored muon beam distribution, contributing to the determination of the magnetic field strength. Trackers are also used to better determine systematic uncertainties as well as perform auxiliary measurements of the muon beam.

Each tracking station consists of 8 trackers which all sit within the storage ring vacuum but outside of the muon beam path. The third type consists of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) probes which are used to measure the magnetic field. There are 378 probes distributed across 72 location above and below the storage ring which continuously measure field drifts during muon storage. A so-called "field trolley" is pulled through the storage ring every 3 to 5 days when there is no muon beam. This provides a map of the field and consists of 17 NMR probes. In addition to the detector setups outlined, a state-of-the-art laser calibration system is used to measure the gain fluctuations at sub-per-mill level precision over a range of timescales from 10ns to the lifetime of the whole experiment. This is done by sending simultaneous calibration pulses onto each of the 1296 crystals of the electromagnetic calorimeters.

2.2 Experimental measurement

A charged particle, when placed in a magnetic field \vec{B} , will traverse in a circular orbit, and its spin will feel a torque causing it to act like a spinning top. As a muon traverses the ring its spin direction precesses ahead of its momentum direction which rotates at the cyclotron frequency. The experiment measures the anomalous precession frequency defined as the difference between the two; this frequency, together with the magnetic field, allows us to determine a_μ

$$\omega_a = \omega_s - \omega_c = a_\mu \frac{e}{m_\mu c} B. \quad (2)$$

The frequency of precession ω_a and the strength of the magnetic field provide the components to calculate the anomalous magnetic moment a_μ . In such an experiment we determine g by measuring a_μ directly; if g were equal to 2 then $a_\mu = 0$ and the spin precession would be equal to the cyclotron frequency.

Due to the spin polarisation of muons and parity violation in weak decays, high-energy positrons are preferentially emitted along the direction of the muon spin. As the muon spin precesses in the magnetic field, the detection and counting of positrons with energies above a specified threshold offer a means to measure the anomalous precession frequency, ω_a . The number of high-energy positrons entering the calorimeters is counted as a function of time and then weighted according to the decay asymmetry that is correlated to the positron energy. This time spectrum (wiggle plot) has an oscillation that is at the ω_a frequency. The highest number of high energy positrons occurs when the spin vector aligns with the momentum vector. To extract ω_a , a multi-parameter fit is performed while accounting for beam oscillations muon losses and detector effects. Each beam-dynamic effect contributes an additional frequency component to the wiggle plot and therefore increases the number of parameters in the fit. Figure 2 shows the oscillation and fit of the detected e^+ time spectrum as well a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the residuals from time-series fits.

The NMR probe is used to measure the magnetic field as a precession frequency (Larmor frequency) ω_p [10]. The ratio of the two frequencies ω_a/ω_p together with reference measurements give the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon, a_μ

$$a_\mu = \frac{\omega_a \mu_p m_p g_e}{\omega_p \mu_e m_e 2} \quad (3)$$

where external well-known constants contribute an overall uncertainty of ~ 25 parts-per-billion (ppb) [11]. From equation 3, one can take into account the motion of the muon beam and transient magnetic fields present in the ring. These effects lead to equation 4

$$a_\mu = \underbrace{\left[\frac{f_{\text{clock}} \cdot \omega_a^m (1 + C_e + C_p + C_{pa} + C_{dd} + C_{ml})}{f_{\text{calib}} \cdot \langle \omega_p(\vec{r}) \times M(\vec{r}) \rangle (1 + B_q + B_k)} \right]}_{\mathcal{R}_\mu} \frac{\mu_p(T_r) \mu_e(H) m_\mu g_e}{\mu_e(H) \mu_e m_e 2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Fourier transform of the residuals from a time-series fit. The red dashed curve shows the result when betatron motion and muon losses are neglected, while the black curve corresponds to the full fit, including these effects. The inset shows e^+ time spectrum (black) from the Run 1c dataset, overlaid with the full fit function (red) [6].

Here, ω_p is fractionally corrected for the quadrupole and kicker transients, B_q and B_k , respectively. B_q describes the vibrations of the ESQ plates that disturb the magnetic field, and B_k accounts for residual eddy currents. Similarly, five correction factors are applied to the measured value of ω_a . The QED factor, $\mu_e(H)/\mu_e$, represents the ratio of the electron's magnetic moment in a hydrogen atom to that of a free electron in vacuum. The reference temperature, $T_r = 25^\circ\text{C}$, is the temperature at which the shielded proton-to-electron magnetic moment ratio, $\mu_p(T_r)/\mu_e(H)$, is measured. Additionally, the muon-to-electron mass ratio m_μ/m_e , has been determined with a precision of 22 ppb using muonium spectroscopy. All corrections, C_i , arise from effects that introduce a frequency bias. These originate from the behaviour of the muon beam, the energy dependence of the positron drift time, and the time dependence of calorimeter acceptance. C_e is the electric field correction needed to account for the spread of the momenta of muons and arises from non-zero electric fields. C_p is the pitch correction which accounts for the vertical oscillation of muons. C_{ml} is the muon loss correction arising from the decay rate of the muons being momentum dependent therefore, affecting the muon initial phase over fill time and biasing ω_a . C_{pa} is the phase acceptance correction arising from the energy dependence of the positron drift time and the time dependence of the calorimeter acceptance. C_{dd} is the differential decay correction which is due to high-momentum muons having a longer lifetime.

The Muon g-2 collaboration employs a blinding technique to prevent unintentional biases in the analysis and to ensure the integrity of its results. This is a hardware blinding done by introducing an unknown frequency offset (Δf) into the clock system used to measure the ω_a frequency. This offset is chosen by a separate independent team and is kept secret until all analysis steps are complete. The unblinding factor is denoted as f_{clock} .

Based on the measurement principle explained above, the analysis is divided into two parts; the measurement of the magnetic field strength ω_p and the measurement and corrections of the anomalous precession frequency ω_a . To minimise errors and use diverse analysis techniques, the ω_a measurement is performed by several independent groups which are then combined at the end taking into account correlations between analysis methods.

Figure 3: Overview of the experimental results for a_μ , the plot shows the Run 1 [6], Run 2/3 result [4] and Run-4/5/6 result [7] as well as the FNAL average of the three. The Brookhaven result [2] is also shown and the combination of all the above is shown as the world average.

2.3 Run-4/5/6 analysis improvements

Data taking and analysis of the Run-4/5/6 dataset brought with it many improvements; some of the most notable are detailed in this section. Compared to the Run 2/3 result, the present measurement benefits first and foremost from a substantially larger dataset. The Run-4/5/6 sample contains more than 2.5 times the positron statistics of the earlier analyses, leading to an improvement in the overall statistical precision by a factor of about 1.8 relative to Run-1/2/3. This increased statistical power, together with dedicated studies, enabled a broader and more stringent set of internal consistency checks across datasets, detector subsystems, and analysis methods.

The largest beam-dynamics effect is the Coherent Betatron Oscillation (CBO), which reflects the radial motion of the beam. The effect was studied extensively by the collaboration. The main challenge in modelling the CBO lies in accurately describing the decoherence of the CBO signal and the time dependence of its frequency. The increased statistics in Run-4/5/6 enabled the testing of more refined models to tackle this challenge. Notably, the addition of horizontal and vertical RF fields drastically reduced the CBO amplitude. The RF system generates dipole fields tuned to the CBO frequency, thereby damping the oscillation. The data are categorised into four RF configurations: no RF, horizontal RF, and horizontal and vertical RF for runs 5 and 6 separately.

A new correction has been included for an intensity-dependent calorimeter gain sag which contributes an uncertainty at the level of 25-40 ppb in the four fit datasets. This calorimeter gain sag also explains some features of the analysis of run-1 [6] and run-2/3 [4] data that had previously not been understood. The effect has been precisely characterised through dedicated laser studies. Although the magnitude of the gain sag remains below the design specification, it oscillates at ω_a with a phase shift relative to the beam intensity, resulting in a higher ω_a sensitivity than previously estimated.

3 Conclusion and outlook

The Muon g-2 Collaboration has achieved an unprecedented precision of 127 ppb in measuring the muon magnetic anomaly using the full six year data taking. The new Run-4/5/6 measurement aligns with both the earlier FNAL results and the Brookhaven experiment (see Figure 3). The muon anomaly is measured to be $a_\mu(\text{Run-4/5/6}) = 116\,592\,0710(162) \times 10^{-12}$ (139 ppb) and $a_\mu(\text{Run-1-6}) = 116\,592\,0705(148) \times 10^{-12}$ (127 ppb).

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